

DESIGN SCHOOL BUILT CHARACTER EDUCATION AWARE OF EARLY CHILDHOOD TRAFFIC

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Abstracts

The culture of road traffic safety is getting worse in Indonesia if you see indications of high numbers of violations and road transport traffic accidents. Early education on the importance of road safety is a way to shape the mindset and character in children to shape people's perceptions and paradigms about road safety. Character education can be used as a reference to make the school's design built by character education aware of early childhood traffic. The research method used is the Cross-Sectional Survey Method, with data retrieval using observations, questionnaires, and interviews. SALUD (Early Age Traffic Conscious) Character Education School Design consisting of instrumental input, environmental input, raw input, transformation, and output can be used as a reference for the implementation of SALUD characters. SALUD character education design assessment is good. The test score measurement results used three variables and six indicators in 9 schools in 4 regions. The results showed that SALUD forms early childhood behaviours well behaved towards families, communities, and the environment.

Keywords: Fostered school, character building, SALUD, survey method

INTRODUCTION

The Global Status Report on Road Safety says that more than 1.25 million people worldwide die because of traffic accidents, and 50 million people are seriously injured. As a result of road accidents in the Republic of Indonesia, an average of 3 people dies every hour. The human factor turned out to be an influential factor in road safety. If there is no awareness and action in the next 20 years, 25 million fatalities will fall (Marroli, 2017). The public should be constantly reminded and refreshed about regulations related to traffic and the risk of traffic violations (Satmiko, 2018). Early education on the importance of road safety is a way to shape the mindset and character in children to shape the perception and paradigm of society about road safety (Kementerian Perhubungan, 2012).

Traffic safety is one of the priorities and joint commitments, as evidenced by the launch of the Decade of Road Safety Action Program consisting of five pillars (Program Dekade Aksi Keselamatan Jalan, 2013). The Early Childhood Traffic Awareness Program (SALUD) is one activity that supports the RAK (Safety Action Plan) program. It can prevent traffic accidents by cultivating a Culture of Traffic Discipline in early childhood (Anonim, 2020). The SALUD (Early Childhood Traffic Conscious) program was established by The Transportation Agency and supported by Presidential Decree No. 4 of 2013 on Road Safety Action 2011-2020. The SALUD program is one of the solutions for traffic behaviour

management applied early on to Learners with the concept of extension, education, and parenting (Yurisdian, 2018).

Character education plays a role in aspects of personality, while the character reflects the personality of a person consisting of mentality, attitude, and behaviour (Berkowitz & Grych, 2000; Lee, 2016; Samuelsson & Carlsson, 2008; Zubaedi, 2011). Failure to cultivate a good personality at an early age will form a problematic person in his adulthood (Prasetyo, 2011). Education based on the character and culture of the nation is an education that applies principles and methodologies towards the formation of the nature of the nation's children in its learners through an integrated curriculum developed in schools (Kaffenberger & Pritchett, 2021; Moser & Zumbach, 2018; Sugita, 2018). School buildings are used as a direct picture to other education units that will apply education quality assurance. There is a pattern of impacting the implementation of quality assurance to all education units in Indonesia (Priambodo, 2019).

The character can be interpreted as innate, heart, soul, personality, ethics, behaviour, nature, essence, temperament, and disposition. Consistency, in this sense, marks and focuses on applying the value of goodness in the form of actions or behaviour (Sugita, 2018). Macro character development is divided into three stages: planning, implementation, and evaluation results. The value/character development program can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Character Development Macro Context (Kementerian Pendidikan Nasional, 2010)

The basis of character education should start at childhood or what psychologists call the golden age. This age has been proven to greatly determine a child's ability to develop his potential (Aktürk & Demircan, 2017; Dennis & Stockall, 2014; Rustini, 2012; Suhonen et al., 2015). Character education is an intentional effort to build individual character so that later they become helpful individuals both for themselves and for many people (Kaimuddin, 2014). The five main characteristics that determine the importance of character education are

religion, nationalism, integrity, independence, and cooperation(Permendiknas, 2009). Character education management design is a strategy that is applied in the development of character education which is carried out with the desire and intention to embody the teachings and noble values to realize the social mission of the madrasa through management activities. The five components are implemented in a concept map management design, and a description of their implementation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flowchart of Madrasah Character Education Management (Wiyani, 2012)

Solutions need to be found to reduce the number of accidents and fatalities on the road (Haryanto, 2021). One of them is through character education in early childhood. Character education can be used as a reference for designing schools targeted for traffic awareness at an early age. The formulation of the problem is how the design of the early childhood Traffic Awareness character education (SALUD) fostered school design and the implementation of the Early Age Traffic Awareness character education school (SALUD). The scope of this research is:

- 1) The target school used is an early childhood education unit (PAUD) for Kindergarten (TK).
- 2) Road transportation safety materials used are road transportation safety socialization materials for ages 3-5 years, published by the Directorate General of Land Transportation, Ministry of Transportation.
- 3) The use of facilities is packaged at the Early Age Traffic Awareness (SALUD) program.

METHODS

The research method is used to gain knowledge using reliable and trustworthy procedures. The type of research used in this research process is the survey method (Kusuma & Setyawati, 2016). This study uses a cross-sectional survey method(Hermawan, 2009). The

survey method is used to obtain data from certain natural places (not made by researchers), but researchers carry out treatments in collecting data. The type of research approach used in the survey and experimental methods is quantitative(Arifin, 2020).

Sample

Samples in this study were early childhood (PAUD) teachers and committee in Ciamis, Bogor, Bekasi, Tegal, and Bandung. The subjects studied were Teachers and Committee in Early Childhood Education. Random sampling was used in this study. The sample consisted of 113 participants. The study was conducted in 4 regions (9 schools), and a total of 113 respondents were obtained with details such as in table 1.

Table1. Data Respondent

No	Region	Schools	Teacher	Committee	Total
1	Kab Ciamis	Ra As Salam	6	4	10
2	Kab Ciamis	Tk Syakiatul	4	3	7
3	Kab Bogor	Tk Alamanda	7	4	11
4	Kab Bogor	Tk Hanifah	9	6	15
5	Kab Bogor	Tk At Taqwa	9	6	15
6	Kota Tegal	Tk Pius	8	6	14
7	Kota Tegal	Tk Pembina Tegal Selatan	6	4	10
8	Kab Bandung	Tk Permata Bunda	9	6	15
9	Kab Bandung	Ra At Toyibah	9	7	16
Total			67	46	113

Collecting Data

The data collection methods used is observations, questionnaires, and interviews. Statements were made on the six elements of SALUD Character Education. The reports will be used to design SALUD character education. Questionnaires were conducted to find out the results of trials on the SALUD character education design application. Questionnaires are filled out by Teachers, Parents (Human Environment), and Managers (management). His judgments include Attitudes and behaviours about God, Attitudes, and behaviours about oneself, Attitudes and behaviours about the family, society, and nation, and attitudes and behaviours about the environment. Interviews are conducted with school managers and trustees. Interviews with school managers contain indicators of socialization, built-up forms, visits to the school, holidays from the school, obstacles, and actions are taken, and expectations. Interviews conducted with school builders contain indicators of socialization, built-up form,

visits to the school, and visits from the school. Variables and indicators for creating SALUD character education design can be seen in table 2.

Table 2: SALUD Character Education Design Variables and Indicators

No	Variable	Indicator
1.	Teacher	Socialization, commitment, context analysis, action plan, program plan, conditioning, and assessment.
2.	Curriculum	Identification and analysis, SALUD formulation in schools, behavior formulation, assessment instruments, communication, and cooperation.
3.	Financing	Inventory of plans, implementation plans, programs and work details, calculation of funds, and determination of sources of funds.
4.	Management	Moral and academic, disciplined, fraternal, mutual respect, increased attention.
5.	Object Environment	Traffic park, traffic safety APE, SALUD material book, SALUD works, and regulations.
6.	Human Environment	Socialization, commitment, action analysis, action plan, program plan, conditioning, assessment.

Data Analysis

SALUD character assessment variables in this study are Teachers, Students, and the Human Environment. There are six indicators of judgment: attitudes and behaviours in relation to God, self, family, society, and nation, and the environment, and the attitude of discipline, order, patience, and not emotion. The instruments used are six, i.e., routine (6), often (5), sometimes (4), rare (3), ever (2), and never (1). The percentage criteria for conformity of the success rate are 5, namely less once (0%-20%), less (21%-40%), enough (41%-60%), good (61%-80%), and excellent (81%-100%). The percentage is obtained from the data calculation formula in formula 1.

$$P = (F/N) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

P is the percentage sought, F is the frequency of respondents' answers, and N is the number of cases.

Results and Discussion

The target schools or SALUD Character Education model schools in this activity are directed and fostered by the Directorate General of Land Transportation, Road Transportation Safety Polytechnic (PKTJ).The Regency or City Transportation Office will become reference schools for other schools in the vicinity in independently implementing education quality

assurance. The agency has not determined the target schools or model schools, as developed by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Higher Education. However, the schools welcomed him voluntarily through the direction given by the resource person during the SALUD technical guidance and advice from the Regency or City Transportation Service. The schools volunteered to be "guided schools," receiving guidance and coaching.

Design of the Assisted School

The design of the SALUD Character Education Assisted School adopts the madrasa character education flow scheme in Figure 2. Adjustments are made based on the indicators described in table 1. The input comes from the school culture, transformed into SALUD character education to produce traffic-aware characters. With five hands of SALUD character assessment. There are also inputs from instrumental (teachers, curriculum, financing, and management) and environmental (object environment and human environment) in the transformation. Each instrumental and environmental has several indicators. These indicators will assess each variable in the instrumental and environment. The design as if the intended target can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Design of SALUD Character Education Supported School

Development of Fostered Schools

The coaching agencies willing to provide direct guidance are the Road Transportation Safety Polytechnic (PKTJ) for Tegal City Trustees and the Transportation Service Ciamis Regency, Bandung Regency, and Bogor Regency. Not all District or City Transportation Offices are actively involved in fostering road transportation safety character education. Implementation

of coaching to schools in coordination with SALUD resource persons, PKTJ, and the Directorate General of Land Transportation.

Coaching can be in outreach activities, direction, coordination, schools, or school visits to the Office of Transportation. Coaching in schools is very dependent on the principal. If the principal is highly motivated and committed, the action in the school will be high. Barriers often found are the availability of educational game tools or learning media. From the interviews with principals and teachers at nine schools, it was found that there was hope for more transparent regulations, attention, and guidance on road safety programs for early childhood. This is so that implementation in schools is more intensive. Coaching in the target schools can be seen in Table 2.

Table 3: Coaching in SALUD Character Education Supported Schools

Schools	Socialization	Built Shape	Go to School	Go from School	Obstacles	Action	Hope
RA As-Salam	Four times	Construction & Coordination	there hasn't been	there hasn't been	APE & media limited	not yet	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Syakiatul	One time	Construction & Coordination	there hasn't been	there hasn't been	APE limited	not yet	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Alamanda	Two times	Coaching, Directing, & Monitoring	exist	exist	APE t limited	some	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Hanifah	Two times	Coaching, Directing, Monitoring, &mentoring	exist	exist	APE & media limited	already	regulation, attention, guidance
TK At-Taqwa	Four times	Coaching, Directing, & Monitoring	exist	exist	APE & media limited	already	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Pius	Two times	Coaching, Directing, Monitoring, Mentoring, Learning & Appointment	exist	there hasn't been	APE limited	already	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Pembina	Three times	Coaching, Direction and Appointment	exist	there hasn't been	APE & media limited	already	regulation, attention, guidance
TK Permata Bunda	Four times	Coaching, Mentoring, & Directing	exist	exist	Lack of visits	already	regulation, attention, guidance
RA At-Thayibbah	Four times	Coaching, Mentoring, & Directing	exist	exist	APE & media limited	already	regulation, attention, guidance

The implementation of character education in schools is very dependent on the attention of the coaching agencies, especially the District or City Transportation Service. The District or City Transportation Service builds SALUD character education closest to PAUD teachers in schools. Kindergarten principals and teachers with little guidance and attention will move with enthusiasm. This follows the characteristics of PAUD teachers who like to instil selfless kindness, compete to build a positive image, and compete to become role models for fellow teachers, children, and parents sincerely in their work. The problem now is that not all regional offices are moved to foster traffic awareness character education in schools.

Assessment of the Design of the Assisted School

There are no criteria for evaluating SALUD Character Education Supported Schools in 4 regions. There is only one that has enough requirements, other than that it has good and excellent standards. The results of the assessment of the SALUD character education target schools showed that the results for the seven assessments were all good criteria. The most prominent assessment is the teacher's assessment in Bandung Regency because it gets an excellent assessment, while the others and the results only have good criteria. Another interesting assessment is the financing assessment in Bogor Regency because compared to others and the result, Bogor Regency has the lowest standards, namely enough. Assessment of SALUD Character Education Supported Schools can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Assessment of SALUD Character Education Supported Schools

If the Transportation Service Officer is conducting the socialization, there are limitations in forming behaviour in PAUD children. The weakness experienced by teachers understands SALUD material, so PAUD teachers must follow SALUD technical guidance. The Directorate General of Land Transportation, the Road Transportation Safety Polytechnic, the Regency, or the City Transportation Service can provide the technical advice. Coordination of teachers with officers in the coaching agency is very much needed. Instrumental input

consists of Teacher Variables, Curriculum, Financing, and Management. Teachers have an outstanding and firm commitment to have a vision for the future to realize character education goals in the schools they carry. The curriculum as input for SALUD character-building schools contains indicators of identification and analysis, formulation of SALUD in schools, formulation of behaviour, assessment instruments, communication, and cooperation. The financing that can be done is that the school and the School Committee conduct an inventory of the budget plan, and then prepare an implementation plan and SALUD character education program. Management is an element of school culture based on SALUD character education. Environmental input includes the object environment and the human environment. Environmental input is objects such as schools providing traffic parks according to school abilities, providing SALUD learning media, providing SALUD educational game tools, availability of SALUD material books, student work on SALUD can motivate teachers, children, and parents. The human environment around children, such as teachers and parents willing to commit, plan, and condition, is well-conditioned.

SALUD Character Education Trial Results

All indicators of SALUD character assessment in 4 regions do not have the criteria of being unfavourable, insufficient, and sufficient. There is a prominent assessment, namely the indicators of attitude and behaviour about the natural surroundings in Bandung Regency, with the criteria of excellent value. In addition, all hands in the four regions and the results have good assessment criteria. SALUD character assessment can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: SALUD Character Assessment

Behaviour related to God, for example, when driving, read a prayer first, because by praying, you hope that road users will be calmer when going. Self-related attitudes and behaviours such as crossing safely are necessary, and wearing a helmet while driving is essential.

Attitudes and behaviors related to family, such as caring for family members to remind them to behave safely on the road. Attitudes and behaviours related to society and the nation, for example, remind other members of the community or are willing to give in when using the road. An attitude related to nature means respecting the road and its equipment as part of the natural environment, not to be damaged and maintained, such as not throwing garbage on the road. Discipline, order, patience, and no emotion are good values. The SALUD character assessment subjects are teachers, parents, and kindergarten children.

CONCLUSION

The design of the SALUD Character Education Assistance School (Early Age Traffic Awareness), which consists of instrumental input, environmental input, raw input, transformation, and output, can be used as a reference for the implementation of the SALUD character. The value of each information: teacher (good), curriculum (good), financing (good), management (excellent), material environment (excellent) and human environment (good). The result of the design assessment is good. The results of the measurement of the test value of the application of the design of the SALUD character education target school using three variables and six indicators in 9 schools in 4 regions showed that the results were good. The results of the SALUD character assessment in 9 target schools showed good results. To fostering agencies and stakeholders, in this case, the Ministry of Transportation, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Religion, Directorate General of Land Transportation, PKTJ, BPTD or local transportation services and regional transportation services, they must coordinate with each other and pay more attention to and make clear regulations regarding traffic safety awareness. Across early childhood. As well as the need for road transportation safety extension workers to accelerate the movement for the formation of road transportation safety behaviour.

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